

Details for registration number : PMOPG/E/2025/0091499

Name Of Complainant	Sardar Dilbag Singh Khalsa
Date of Receipt	28/06/2025
Received By Ministry/Department	Prime Minister's Office
Grievance Description	
<p>Consumer Affairs >> Consumer Protection Unit Related >> Miscellaneous</p> <p>-----</p> <p>I enrolled myself into my shadi app and paid 4000. It was clickbait not any single girl accepts invitation. In ad they promised to money back guaranty in 30 days , but now they are refusing to refund the amount. Their app claims that costumer will get suitable match, but I don't get any suitable match. They have done false promise to me. I am manipulated by them. Kindly direct them to refund my amount and provide me compensation for mental agony.</p>	
Current Status	Case closed
Date of Action	29/07/2025
Remarks	
<p>The grievance was taken up with the company by NCH and the company has responded that We have refunded the membership from our side on 15-Jul-2025 and it will reflect in your source account in 7-10 working days. Refund transaction is com_shaadi-175097939881-1 Please treat this complaint as CLOSED. Consumer Helpline (NCH) is an effective pre-litigation mechanism to resolve the grievance, which makes efforts by approaching the company. If you are not satisfied with the response of company, it is advised that you may approach Consumer Commission for redressal of your grievances/compensation etc, online at https://e-jagriti.gov.in. Consumer Protection Act empowers Consumer Commissions (National/State/District) to give compensation and to impose fine etc. This is a user friendly on-line platform with virtual court integration, on-line hearing and without any need of advocate etc. Process is free of cost for case value upto Rs 5 Lakh.</p>	
Officer Concerns To	

Officer Name	Mr. Manish Gupta (Project Manager)
Organisation name	National Consumer Helpline
Contact Address	Krishi BhawanDelhiNew Delhi
Email Address	support-nch2@gov.in
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